

The EUDATA+ Cluster unites six projects on data monetisation and exchange, fostered by the European Commission’s push for collaboration under programmes like Horizon Europe. Beyond coordination, it now drives shared goals and knowledge transfer, maximising impact and enhancing the development of data-sharing technologies.

DATA LIFECYCLE

DATA PROVIDER

Data Ingestion

Data Enrichment

Data Product Creation and Preparation

Data Publication

DATA EXCHANGE

Data Exchange Environment

DATA CONSUMER

Data Acquisition

Data Consumption

Working groups of the EUDATA+ cluster

TECH GROUP

Scientific and Technical Collaboration

ECOSYSTEM GROUP

Communication & Dissemination and Community Building

BUSINESS GROUP

Exploitation, Business topics & Strategies

Meet the projects

PISTIS is a European project developing a secure platform for organizations to share, trade, and monetize proprietary data. It leverages federated data sharing, DLTs, data NFTs, and AI-driven quality assessment to build trust and address stakeholder concerns.

FAME unites experts in data management, the data economy, and digital finance to overcome cloud marketplace limitations. It will provide an OpenAPI-based federated data marketplace, accessible publicly and supporting diverse data assets in a multi-provider cloud environment.

UPCAST provides transparent, user-friendly plugins to automate data sharing and processing agreements across businesses, governments, and citizens. It supports European data spaces by integrating advanced research in data management, privacy, monetization, and compliance with AI regulations and ethical standards.

enRichMyData

enRichMyData provides an open toolbox with scalable components to help organizations enrich their data and support data providers in improving reusability. It lowers technological barriers by enabling scalable data enrichment pipelines, making the process more accessible and user-friendly.

datamite

DATAMITE offers a modular, open-source framework, complete with software modules, training, and business materials, to boost data monetisation, interoperability, trading, and exchange. It empowers European SMEs, large enterprises, and public administrations to better govern, trust, and profit from their data, aiming to transform the European Data Market.

Graph-Massivizer develops a scalable, sustainable platform for processing extreme data as massive graphs. It provides five open-source tools and FAIR graph datasets for data ingestion, graph creation, automated intelligence, performance modeling, and sustainability, ensuring usability and efficiency across the computing continuum.

Scan the QR code to learn more about the EUDATA+ cluster and the projects involved!

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